

DESIGN AND EVALUATION OF CONTROLLED RELEASE MATRIX TABLETS OF NIZATIDINE BY USING POLYMERS - HPMC K4M, CARBOPOL-934 AND GUARGUM

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Received on: 11-11-2015; Revised and Accepted on: 28-12-2015

ABSTRACT

Nizatidine is used in the treatment of Zollinger-Ellison Syndrome, Gastro Esophageal Reflux Disease, Duodenal and Gastric, Peptic ulcers. It is Histamine (H-2) receptor antagonist. Oral administration of Nizatidine is absorbed incompletely from the GI tract. Oral administration favors controlled release due to low Biological half life (1-2 hrs) and high Bioavailability (70%). Nizatidine controlled release matrix tablets prepared by using a Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose (HPMC K4M), Carbopol-934 as hydrophilic polymer and Guar gum as natural polymer with three different concentrations (Drug: polymers 1:0.5, 1:0.75 and 1:1) by using Wet granulation method. The prepared granules were evaluated for pre-compression properties. The tablets were subjected to evaluate post compression properties. In-vitro drug release studies were evaluated to compare the Nizatidine formulations (N1-N10) with available marketed product. Among all the prepared formulations, high proportion of Guar gum (1:1)(N6) was able to control drug delivery for 24 hours (94.2%). In-vitro drug release data fitting to kinetic analysis, mechanism of all the formulations followed to both Diffusion and Erosion¹⁰. All formulations were stored at 40 ± 2 °C, 75 ± 5%RH, conducted to stability studies upto 6 months. Results showed that all the formulations are stable for physically and chemically.

KEYWORDS: Nizatidine, Controlled Release, Peptic Ulcer, Zollinger Ellison Syndrome, Gastro-Esophageal Reflux Disease, Duodenal Ulcer.

INTRODUCTION

Nizatidine is a potent H-2 receptor Antagonist used in the management of Benign Gastric and Duodenal ulceration, Zollinger-Ellison Syndrome and Gastro Esophageal Reflux Disease. Conventional oral formulations of Nizatidine are administered multiple times a day. Treatment of gastric acid secretion using conventional formulations of Nizatidine is found to have many drawbacks, such as adverse side effects resulting from accumulation of drug in multidose therapy and poor patient compliance. Controlled release^[6] formulations of Nizatidine can overcome some of these problems. The matrix tablets can be prepared by Wet granulation method^[1]. Among many polymers used in the formulation of matrix based CR drug delivery systems, hydrophilic and natural polymer matrix systems are widely used because of their flexibility to obtain a desirable drug release profile, cost effectiveness and broad regulatory acceptance. Guar gum a natural polymer is first choice for formulation of controlled drug release matrix system providing robust mechanism, choice of viscosity grades, nonionic nature, consistent reproducible release profile, cost effectiveness and utilization of existing conventional equipment and methods. Water penetration, polymer swelling, drug dissolution, drug diffusion and matrix erosion from dosage form is controlled natural polymer, which forms the gel barrier through which the drug diffuses.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials:

Nizatidine was a gift sample from Hetero Pharma India Pvt Ltd, Hyderabad, India. HPMC K4M, Guar gum, Carbopol-934 from KP labs, Talc and Magnesium Stearate were procured from Saraswathi Chemicals Pvt Ltd; Mumbai, India. Lactose, Poly Vinyl Pyrrolidone and Isopropyl Alcohol were procured from S.D Fine Chemicals. Pvt Ltd; Mumbai, India. All other chemicals and reagents used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of Nizatidine CR Matrix Tablets:

Nine formulations of controlled release tablets of Nizatidine using HPMC K4M, Carbopol-934 and Guar gum with three ratios (1:0.5, 1:0.75, 1:1) were prepared by Wet granulation method. The details of composition of each formulation are shown in Table-1. Nizatidine and polymers were mixed separately. Lactose were added to the drug polymer mixture and blended thoroughly for 5 minutes. Poly Vinyl Pyrrolidone (PVP) was dissolved in sufficient quantity of Isopropyl Alcohol (IPA) until it forms a solution and this was added to the drug mixture and mixed thoroughly to form a coherent mass. Then the coherent mass was passed through Sieve No: 16 to form granules and the collected granules were dried at 40°C±2°C for 2 hours. The dried granules were passed through sieve No: 22 and retained granules were evaluate pre-compression properties for Bulk density, Tapped density, Angle of repose^[2], Compressibility index and Hausener's ratio^[12] (Table-7 and 8). Then the granules were mixed with Magnesium Stearate, Talc and finally compressed into tablets. The same procedure was followed to prepare Nizatidine tablets without polymer (Control).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Nizatidine CR Tablets:

1. UV Spectrophotometric Detection (λ_{max}) for Nizatidine Pure Drug:

50 µg/ml of drug solution is scanned in Ultra Violet range between 200-400 nm. Maximum absorption observed at 325nm.

Table No. 1: Formulation of Various Nizatidine CR Matrix Tablets by Wet Granulation Method (N-1 to N-10)

Ingredients(mg)	N1	N2	N3	N4	N5	N6	N7	N8	N9	N10
Nizatidine	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
HPMC K4M	50	75	100							-
Guargum				50	75	100				-
Carbapol -934							50	75	100	-
Eudragit	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Lactosemonohydrate	131	106	81	131	106	81	131	106	81	181
Magnesium Stearate	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Talc	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
PVPK-30	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Isopropyl Alcohol	Q.s									
Total (mg)	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300

Drug: Polymers ratios – 1:0.5, 1:0.75, 1:1 (N1, N2, N3 - N4, N5, N6 - N7, N8, N6 respectively) (N10-Without polymers)

Fig. 1: Standard calibration curve of Nizatidine

Table No. 2: Quantitative Parameters of Spectrophotometric Method

Parameter	Value
λ_{max}	325 nm
Beers law limit ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	05-40
Regression Equation	$Y = 0.025x + 0.005$
Slope	0.025
Intercept	0.005
Correlation coefficient	0.998

Table No. 3: Calibration Curve Data for Nizatidine

S.no	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance	SD	% RSD
1	0	0	0	0
2	10	0.251	0.00171	0.8967
3	20	0.506	0.00213	1.2076
4	30	0.630	0.00479	1.2198
5	40	0.851	0.00864	2.4106
6	50	1.121	0.01289	2.6453

2. Drug - Excipients Compatibility studies of Nizatidine:

2.1. Fourier Transform Infra-Red Spectroscopy (FTIR):

This spectrum was recorded for 1:1 ratio of physical mixtures by using Nizatidine and polymers like HPMC K4M, Guar gum and Carbapol-934. KBr pellets (2 mg sample in 200 mg KBr) are used to prepare the samples with help of a hydrostatic force of 5.2 N cm^{-2} for 3 minutes. The scanning wavelength was 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} and the resolution was 4 cm^{-1} .

The IR spectral studies of pure Nizatidine drug and combinations of Nizatidine with polymers were carried out to assess any interaction between the polymer and drug used. N-H stretching of primary amine, C-H stretching, C-S stretching, C-H deformation, N-H out of plane bending of pure Nizatidine and Nizatidine with polymer were almost in the same wave number region ranging from 608 cm^{-1} to 3402 cm^{-1} .

This interpretation confirms that there was no interaction significantly between polymer and drug and they were found to be compatible with each other Table 4.

2.2. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) Studies of Nizatidine:

Pure drug, excipients and their physical mixtures of (1:1) were sealed in aluminum pan and scanned between 25°C and 300°C with heating rate of 10°C per minute under an atmosphere of dry nitrogen. Any interaction can be observed to obtain the thermograms (Fig. 3, 4 & Table 5).

DSC studies were carried out to detect interaction between Nizatidine and excipients. The thermogram of Nizatidine exhibited a sharp endotherm melting point at 136°C . Also, the thermogram of Nizatidine formulation exhibited a sharp endotherm melting point at 134°C .

There is no considerable change observed in melting endotherm of drug in optimized formulation. It indicates there is no significant interaction between drug and excipient in the formulation (Fig. 5 & Table 6).

Fig. 2: FTIR Spectra of Nizatidine and Excipients

Table No. 4: Interpretation of FTIR Results: Pure Drug Nizatidine with Polymers (HPMC K4M, Guargum, Carbopol-934)

S.no	Functional Group	Range(cm ⁻¹)	Observed Peak (cm ⁻¹)
1	N-H Stretching	3400-3500	3434.28
2	C-H Stretching (Alkane)	2880-3000	2955.98
3	C-H Stretching (Alkene)	2800-3000	2851.12
4	N=C=S Stretching	1990-2140	2032.29
5	C=C Stretching	1638-1648	1638.28
6	C-N Stretching	1020-1250	1023.36

Fig. 3: DSC Thermogram of Nizatidine Pure Drug

Fig. 4: DSC Thermogram of Optimized Formulated Nizatidine

Table No. 5: Melting Point of Drug Nizatidine and Optimized Formulation

Name of the Ingredient	Melting Point
Nizatidine pure drug	136°C
Formulated Nizatidine	134°C

Fig. 5: DSC Thermogram of Drug Nizatidine and Polymers (HPMC K4M, Guargum and Carbopol-934)

Table No. 6: T_{peak} observed in Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) Thermograms of Nizatidine, polymers and Mixture of Both (1:1)

S.no	Sample	T _{peak} (°C) Drug	T _{peak} (°C) Polymer
1	Nizatidine	138.4°C	
2	HPMC K4M		224.6°C
3	Nizatidine + HPMC K4M	171.4°C	
4	Guargum		118.9°C
5	Nizatidine + Guargum	124.4°C	
6	Carbopol-934		121.1°C
7	Nizatidine + Carbopol-934	127.5°C	

DSC thermograms comprising mixture of drug-excipient do not exhibit any appreciable changes in peak value. Nizatidine showed a sharp endothermic peak (T_{peak}) at 138.4°C. In presence of pure drug, the thermograms⁹ showed sharp peak in up curve on the base line and any impurities present in the thermogram may show down curve from base line. Quantity of material and drug-excipient mixtures may influence the shape of peak and enthalpy. Hence, it may be concluded that the presence of excipients in drug-excipient mixture may have shown slight changes in melting endotherm, but not significant.

2.3. X-Ray Powder Diffraction (X-RPD) Studies of Nizatidine:

XRPD studies were carried out for tracing the drug Nizatidine on XRD patterns using standards, Cu K (α) Radiation, Nickel is used as a filter and voltage of kv, a current of 20 Ma and receiving slit of 0.2 inch. The samples were analyzed over 2θ range of 10° to 100°, with scan step size of 0.020 (2θ) and scan step time of one second. The intensity of the peak in Nizatidine was found to be 4126 in 27°.

Fig. 6: XRPD Studies of Nizatidine Drug

3. Pre-Compression Properties of the Powder Blend:

Table No. 7: Pre-compression properties of Nizatidine Powder Blend (N1to N5)

Parameters	N1	N2	N3	N4	N5
Bulk Density(gm/cc)	0.64±0.11	0.67±0.11	0.57±0.31	0.59±0.22	0.56±0.18
Tapped Density(gm/cc)	0.86 ±0.63	0.88±0.24	0.81±0.13	0.83±0.81	0.81±0.17
Angle of Repose(θ)	29.61±0.29	28.63±0.35	28.01±0.29	29.05±0.06	28.59±0.63
Compressibility Index (%)	11.5±0.39	11.8±0.21	10.6±0.17	11.9±0.15	11.6±0.11
Hausener's Ratio	0.744	0.761	0.703	0.710	0.691

All values as mean± standard deviation, n=5

Table No. 8: Pre-compression Properties of Nizatidine Powder Blend (N6 to N10)

Parameters	N6	N7	N8	N9	N10
Bulk Density(gm/cc)	0.63±0.21	0.65±0.63	0.60±0.39	0.57±0.73	0.60±0.87
Tapped Density(gm/cc)	0.85±0.21	0.86±0.13	0.84±0.29	0.81±0.49	0.83±0.22
Angle of Repose(θ)	27.89±0.11	28.33±0.52	27.85±0.33	27.10±0.67	27.62±0.23
Compressibility Index (%)	10.8±0.12	10.4±0.35	12.5±0.22	10.6±0.81	10.7±0.67
Hausener's Ratio	0.741	0.779	0.714	0.703	0.722

All the values as mean ± standard deviation, n = 5

Bulk Density:

Estimation of Bulk density by done by using graduated cylinder. The bulk drug was poured in the cylinder and the weight and volume measured. Mechanical tapper apparatus¹¹ was used to determine the Tapped density. Known mass of drug or formulation was placed in a graduated cylinder which is operated for number of fixed taps (approx 1000) until volume of powder bed reached a minimum. Using the minimum volume of drug in cylinder, the Tapped density may be computed.

$$\text{Bulk density} = \text{Volume of the bulk powder} / \text{Mass of powder}$$

$$\text{Tapped density} = \text{Tapped powder volume} / \text{Powder mass}$$

Powder Flow Properties:

The critical role of flow properties of powders is an efficient tableting operation. The compressed tablets are formed by efficient mixing and acceptable uniformity of weight due to good powder flow characteristics. In preformulation stage if a drug was "poorly flowable," the problem can be rectified by excipients selected.

Angle of Repose:

"Angle of repose" is defined as the maximum angle which is formed between horizontal surface and the surface of pile.

Most of the pharmaceutical powders range from 25 to 45°, with indication of lower values to good flow characteristics.

$$\tan \theta = h / r$$

h = Heap of pile height, r = Base of pile radius.

Compressibility Index:

The ability to reduce powder volume under pressure is called as Compressibility. The ability to compress the powdered material into a tablet by using specified tensile strength⁴ is called as compactability.

Flow properties can be predicted based on density measurement by using compressibility.

$$\text{Carr's compressibility Index} = 100 \times [\text{Tapped density} - \text{Bulk density}] / \text{Tapped density}$$

Table No. 9: Carr's Compressibility Index

S.no	% (Percentage) of Compressibility	Relative Flow Ability
1	5-15	Excellent
2	12-16	Good
3	18 -21	Fair
4	23-28	Slightly poor
5	28-35	Poor
6	35-38	Very poor
7	More than 40	Extremely poor

Discussion:

- Bulk density values ranges between 0.56 - 0.67 gm/cc
- Tapped density values ranges between 0.88 - 0.81 gm/cc
- Compressibility index values ranges between 10.6 -12.5 %
- Hausner's ratio values ranges between 0.691-0.761
- Angle of repose values ranges between 27.10° - 29.63°, which indicates these properties of powder, was good flow.

4. Evaluation Post- Compression Properties of Nizatidine Matrix tablets:

Table No. 10: Post Compression Nizatidine Matrix Tablets (N1 to N5)

Parameters	N1	N2	N3	N4	N5
Hardness (kg/cm ²)	5.01±0.14	5.04±0.29	5.12±0.09	5.09±0.61	5.04±0.31
Friability (%)	0.24±0.06	0.26±0.04	0.21±0.04	0.23±0.05	0.29±0.03
Weight Variation (mg)	299.6±4.2	299.1±3.6	299.7±2.9	299.5±3.0	299.3±3.6
Content Uniformity (%)	99.45±0.33	97.12±0.12	99.23±0.27	99.48±0.11	96.13±0.23
Thickness (mm)	4.1±0.03	4.1±0.29	4.3±0.51	4.6±0.31	4.2±0.26
Diameter (mm)	9.2±0.02	9.3±0.03	9.1±0.02	9.3±0.05	9.2±0.01

(Standard Deviation, n±5)

Table No. 11: Post Compression Properties Nizatidine Matrix Tablets (N6 to N10)

Parameters	N6	N7	N8	N9	N10
Hardness (kg/cm ²)	5.03±0.79	5.19±0.03	5.03±0.33	5.07±0.89	5.16±0.66
Friability (%)	0.36±0.06	0.26±0.09	0.29±0.05	0.31±0.01	0.33±0.33
Weight Variation (mg)	299.3±3.1	299.4±2.2	299.7±3.0	299.0±2.5	299.6±2.7
Content Uniformity (%)	99.01±0.37	98.03±0.81	98.96±0.11	98.90±0.56	99.11±0.21
Thickness (mm)	4.3±0.61	4.2±0.33	4.2±0.26	4.4±0.11	4.0±0.29
Diameter (mm)	9.1±0.03	9.0±0.07	9.1±0.03	9.2±0.01	9.1±0.03

(Standard Deviation, n±5)

Discussion:

- Tablets hardness values ranges between 5.01 - 5.19 kg/cm²
- Tablets friability values ranges between 0.21 - 0.33 %
- Tablets content uniformity values ranges between 99.48 - 96.13 mg
- Tablets weight variation ranges between 299.1-299.7 mg
- Tablets thickness values ranges between 4.0-4.6 mm
- Tablets diameter values ranges between 9.1-9.4 mm

All formulations, evaluation parameters were found to be within the acceptable ranges; therefore tablets can be deemed to with good strength physically.

4.1. Hardness:

The Hardness test was performed by using Monsanto hardness test apparatus by testing tablet fixed between moving jaws. The force required breaking the tablet and screw knob moved forward to the indicator is shown to reading valve.

4.2. Friability:

Roche friabilator^[8] was used to perform by friability test. Weighed ten tablets were placed in the friabilator and operated for 25rpm upto 100 revolutions. The tablets were de-dusted and reweighed.

$$\% \text{ friability} = 100 \times (W_i - W_f) / W_i$$

Where, W_i = Intial weight, W_f = Final weight

4.3. Weight Variation:**5. Dissolution Data of Nizatidine CR Matrix tablets (N1-N10):****Table No. 12: Dissolution Data of Prepared Nizatidine Matrix Tablet Formulations (N1 to N5)**

Time in (Hrs)	N1	N2	N3	N4	N5
1	12.4±1.23	12.2±1.04	12.0±1.03	11.1±1.11	10.5±1.24
2	17.4±1.91	17.1±1.23	16.8±1.92	16.2±1.43	15.8±1.14
3	23.2±1.26	23.1±1.76	22.9±1.27	22.2±1.33	21.9±1.56
4	32.9±1.72	32.6±1.26	32.3±1.36	31.6±1.56	31.5±1.64
5	37.6±1.23	37.4±1.54	37.1±1.26	36.1±1.83	35.8±1.42
6	42.7±1.96	42.4±1.27	42.2±1.11	40.8±1.02	40.6±1.46
7	48.6±1.12	48.5±1.56	48.3±1.09	47.5±1.56	47.3±1.64
8	53.2±1.54	53.1±1.22	52.7±1.09	52.6±1.82	52.2±1.47
9	56.6±1.42	56.2±1.76	55.8±1.39	55.4±1.70	54.8±1.39
10	59.6±1.99	59.4±1.37	59.1±1.43	58.4±1.22	58.1±1.02
11	63.4±1.19	63.1±1.34	62.7±1.12	60.9±1.20	60.7±1.04
12	68.9±1.41	68.9±1.26	68.3±1.41	66.5±1.04	66.3±1.32
14	73.2±1.11	72.8±1.51	72.7±1.16	71.3±1.17	70.7±1.18
16	78.4±1.71	78.1±1.18	77.8±1.21	76.1±1.20	75.8±1.20
18	82.6±1.54	82.4±1.12	82.1±1.34	80.4±1.08	80.1±1.18
20	88.6±1.26	88.5±1.32	88.2±1.81	84.8±1.24	84.5±1.24
22	92.8±1.64	92.6±1.10	92.1±1.32	89.6±1.01	89.4±1.32
24	97.5±1.06	97.4±1.22	97.1±1.19	94.7±1.06	94.4±1.42

Table-13 Dissolution Data of Prepared Nizatidine Matrix Tablet Formulations (N6 to N10)

Time in (Hrs)	N6	N7	N8	N9	N10
1	10.2±1.03	11.9±1.04	11.6±1.23	11.4±1.11	23.4±1.24
2	15.4±1.92	16.4±1.23	16.1±1.91	16.0±1.43	38.7±1.14
3	21.7±1.27	22.7±1.76	22.6±1.26	22.3±1.33	54.6±1.56
4	31.2±1.36	32.1±1.26	31.9±1.72	31.7±1.56	69.2±1.64
5	35.3±1.26	37.7±1.54	37.2±1.23	36.8±1.83	74.6±1.42
6	40.2±1.11	42.2±1.27	41.8±1.96	41.4±1.02	89.8±1.46
7	47.1±1.09	48.7±1.56	48.6±1.12	48.5±1.56	96.9±1.64
8	52.1±1.09	53.5±1.22	53.3±1.54	53.2±1.82	99.7±1.39
9	55.4±1.39	56.7±1.76	56.3±1.42	55.9±1.70	-
10	57.3±1.43	58.8±1.37	58.5±1.99	58.2±1.22	-
11	60.4±1.03	62.2±1.28	62.2±1.11	61.9±1.16	-
12	66.1±1.26	68.1±1.32	68.0±1.46	67.7±1.25	-
14	70.4±1.16	73.4±1.51	73.1±1.62	72.9±1.52	-
16	75.5±1.02	78.5±1.06	78.3±1.18	78.1±1.13	-
18	79.7±1.26	82.7±1.44	82.6±1.21	82.3±1.01	-
20	84.1±1.14	88.4±1.28	88.2±1.62	87.9±1.42	-
22	89.1±1.22	92.1±1.04	91.8±1.51	91.7±1.63	-
24	94.2±1.42	97.4±1.09	97.2±1.00	96.9±1.19	-

Dissolution Release Profile:

In-vitro drug release studies were performed by using USP apparatus Type II at 50 rpm. 900ml of phosphate buffer pH-7.4 was used as dissolution medium^[7] and temperature was maintained at 37±0.5°C. The amount of drug release was determined by taking 5ml sample (which was replaced with same amount of fresh medium) every one-hour interval upto 24 hours and suitably diluted with 7.4 pH phosphate buffer. All the samples were subjected to measurement of absorbance at 325 nm using Ultra Violet spectrophotometer.

In-vitro drug release data was used to calculate the percentage (%) of drug delivered from Nizatidine matrix tablet formulations with polymer, Marketed tablet and Nizatidine tablet formulation without polymer (Control). Results of the *in-vitro* release³ studies of Nizatidine matrix tablet formulations with polymer were presented in (Table 12 & 13).

In this test, Selected 20 tablets were randomly weighed individually. The weights of individual tablets were compared with that of average weight.

4.4. Drug Content:

Weighed 10 tablets were powdered. 100mg equivalent Nizatidine powder was dissolved in 10ml of 0.1M HCl, then make up to volume with phosphate buffer pH-7.4 up to 100ml in a standard volumetric flask. From this 10µg/ml, equivalent solution was prepared and determined at 325 nm using UV spectrophotometer.

The percentage (%) of drug release from all formulations after 24 hours using HPMC K4M as polymer was found to be 97.5 % (N1), 97.4% (N2) and 97.1 % (N3). Also, It was found that the cumulative % of drug delivery of the formulation N1 was more than N2 and N3. The cumulative % of drug delivery in the formulation N3 showed better controlled release than N1 and N2.

Drug release in formulation comprising natural polymer Guargum was found to be 94.7% (N4), 94.4 % (N5), and 94.2% (N6). It was found that the cumulative % drug delivery of the formulation N4 was more than N5 and N6. The cumulative % of drug delivery in the formulation N6 showed more controlled release than N4 and N5.

Drug release in formulation comprising hydrophilic polymer carbopol-934 was found to be 97.4% (N7), 97.2 % (N8), and 96.9% (N9). It was found that the cumulative % drug delivery of the formulation N7 was more than N8 and N9. The cumulative % of drug delivery in the formulation N9 showed controlled release than

N7 and N8. On comparison among all formulations (N9) showed better controlled release.

The Guargum (1:1) polymer formulation (N6) exhibited better controlled release compared to HPMC K4M and Carbopol-934 polymer formulations. It is understood that the concentration of polymer played a crucial role in drug release. At higher polymer

concentration, the drug delivery was prolonged or extended compared to formulations with less concentration of the polymer.

In-vitro dissolution studies of Nizatidine (without polymer) tablet formulation (control) exhibited 99.7% of drug release in 8 hrs, where as the Nizatidine release from marketed matrix tablet was 99.2% in 20 hrs.

Fig. 7: Dissolution profile of Nizatidine CR Tablets Formulations from N-1 to N-10

Table No. 14: Comparison Dissolution Data profile of Optimized formulation and Marketed Product (Tazac)

Time (hrs)	Optimized Formulations (N6)	Marketed Product(Tazac)
1	10.2±1.11	12.8±1.21
2	15.4±1.43	18.5±1.08
3	21.7±1.33	24.9±1.36
4	31.2±1.56	29.6±1.61
5	35.3±1.83	35.5±1.34
6	40.2±1.02	41.4±1.06
7	47.1±1.02	46.9±1.42
8	52.1±1.56	53.1±1.62
9	55.4±1.82	59.5±1.26
10	57.8±1.70	66.1±1.01
11	60.4±1.22	71.2±1.06
12	66.1±1.16	76.8±1.32
14	70.4±1.25	82.7±1.27
16	75.5±1.52	87.5±1.16
18	79.7±1.13	93.4±1.48
20	84.1±1.42	99.2±1.12
22	89.1±1.92	-
24	94.2±1.19	-

Fig. 8: Comparison of Nizatidine (CR) Marketed Product (Tazac) and Optimized Formulation

6. Kinetic Analysis:

The mechanism of drug release among all formulations was assessed by fitting the results of *in-vitro* release profiles into

Zero order kinetics, First order kinetic model, Higuchi model [5], and Korsmeyer models. The results of kinetic models data were plotted against *in-vitro* drug release profiles treatment as follows:

1. Cumulative % drug release on y-axis Vs time on x-axis (Zero Order Kinetic Model).
2. Log cumulative % drug remaining on y-axis Vs time on x-axis (First Order Kinetic Model).
3. Cumulative % drug release on y-axis Vs square root of time on x-axis (Higuchi Model).
4. Log cumulative % drug released on y-axis Vs log time on x-axis (Korsmeyer Model).

The delivery rate of kinetic data for all the preparations were shown in Table-15. When the data were plotted against to Zero order, the preparations showed a high linearity, with Regression co-efficient values (R²) between 0.9832-0.9986.

In-vitro drug release data plotted against to First order, the formulations showed with Regression co-efficient values (R²) between 0.9422-0.9716.

Concentration of *in-vitro* drug release studies depending on diffusion explained by Higuchi's model. All the preparation of drug delivery profiles could be best explained by Higuchi's equations, as the plot showed all values high linearity with Regression co-efficient (R²) between 0.9422-0.9716.

By using Korsmeyer model, if "n" value is not more than 0.45, it is Fickian diffusion, if n = 0.45-0.89 it is non-Fickian transport. The result of all the preparations showed 'n' values between 0.516-0.896. It showed that all formulations follow Non-Fickian transport mechanism and also combination of both Erosion and Diffusion release mechanism (Table-15).

Table No. 15: Kinetic Data Analysis for Nizatidine CR Matrix Tablet Formulations

Formulation Code	Regression Coefficient(R)			Korsmeyer peppas Model	
	Zero order	First order	Higuchi's	R ²	Slope
N1	0.9854	0.9565	0.9769	0.6818	0.576
N2	0.9906	0.9595	0.9846	0.7114	0.665
N3	0.9965	0.9674	0.9536	0.7583	0.826
N4	0.9813	0.9480	0.9865	0.6776	0.516
N5	0.9832	0.9525	0.9716	0.6816	0.534
N6	0.9906	0.9465	0.967	0.7196	0.602
N7	0.9870	0.9515	0.9846	0.6880	0.630
N8	0.9902	0.9535	0.9491	0.7016	0.664
N9	0.9986	0.9716	0.9526	0.7886	0.896
N10	0.9876	0.9422	0.9862	0.7686	0.686

Kinetics of Drug Delivery of Optimized (N-6) Formulation:

6.1. Zero Order:

Fig. 9: Zero Order Plot Nizatidine Optimized Formulation (N-6)

6.2. First Order:

Fig. 10: First Order Plot Nizatidine Optimized Formulation (N6)

6.3. Higuchi Model:

Fig. 11: Higuchi Plot Nizatidine Optimized Formulation (N6)

6.4. Korsmeyer-Peppas Model:

Fig. 12: Korsmayer-peppas Plot Nizatidine Optimized Formulation (N6)

Table No. 16: Drug Release Kinetics of Nizatidine Optimized CR Matrix Tablet Formulations N-6

Formulation	Zero order (r ²)	First order (r ²)	Higuchi model (r ²)	Korsmayer-Peppas model		Best fit model
				r ²	"n" value	
N-6	0.990	0.946	0.967	0.719	0.602	Zero order

7. Stability Study of Nizatidine CR tablets:

Table No. 17: Summary of Stability Data (As per ICH Guidelines)

Study	Storage conditions	Minimum time period
General case	25°C (±2°C) at 60% RH(±5%RH)	12 months
Long term	30°C (±2°C) at 65% RH(±5%RH)	12 months
Intermediate	30°C (±2°C) at 65% RH(±5%RH)	6 months
Accelerated	40°C (±2°C) at 75% RH(±5%RH)	6 months

(I) Accelerated Stability studies were conducted on Nizatidine optimized controlled release 300mg tablets, which were collected in HDPE air tight container and maintained in storage conditions at 40°C / 75 % RH for 180 days or 6 months.

Table No. 18: Stability Data for Optimized Nizatidine CR tablets (N6)

S.no	Stability Testing	Specifications	Initial	Time interval in months		
				1	3	6
1	Description	White crystalline powder	Complies	Complies	Complies	Complies
2	Thickness(mm)	4.0-4.5 mm	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4
3	Hardness(mm)	4.5-5.5 mm	5.7	5.7	5.7	5.6
4	Friability %	0.1-0.8	0.31	0.31	0.31	0.31
5	Weight variation (mg)	270-330	299	299	299	298
6	Dissolution					
	2 nd hr	B/W 10%-25%	15.4	15.4	15.4	15.5

4 th hr	B/W 20%-35%	31.2	31.2	31.2	31.4
8 th hr	B/W 30%-45%	52.1	52.1	52.1	52.4
12 th hr	B/W 50%-65%	66.1	66.1	66.1	66.2
24 th hr	NLT 80%	94.2	94.2	94.2	94.4

CONCLUSION

The results of experimental studies of Nizatidine matrix tablets proved that the granules of Nizatidine showed good flow properties, evaluation tests of tablets are within the acceptable limits, Infra Red (IR) spectral analysis proved that there was no polymer-drug interaction. Kinetic studies of all formulations were followed zero order drug release. Stability analysis revealed that all formulations were found to be stable after storing at 40°C / 75 % RH for 180 days. The main drawbacks of the conventional dosage forms of Nizatidine can be minimized by Nizatidine Controlled Release tablets. Thus the results of the above study clearly indicated that Nizatidine may be formulated as CR matrix tablets by using different polymers HPMC K4M (N1-N3), Guargum (N4-N6), Carbapol-934 (N7-N9) by Wet granulation method. In all formulations are compared to dissolution data studies the natural polymer Guargum (N-6) (1:1) provides continuous release of drug at predetermined rate and time.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are thankful to Hetero Labs Private Limited, Hyderabad, Mumbai, India for providing a sample of Nizatidine and Shadan college of Pharmacy for providing necessary facilities to carry out the work

Abbreviations:

HPMC – Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose, CR – Controlled Release, RH - Relative Humidity, UV- Ultra Violet

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How to cite this article:

M. Hareesh Reddy, Dr. A. Sambasivarao. DESIGN AND EVALUATION OF CONTROLLED RELEASE MATRIX TABLETS OF NIZATIDINE BY USING POLYMERS - HPMC K4M, CARBOPOL-934 AND GUARGUM. J Sci Res Pharm 2015;4(8):139-148.

Conflict of interest: The authors have declared that no conflict of interest exists.

Source of support: Nil